

Recurring Microlensing Events in the Galactic Bulge

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ABSTRACT

Annually, up to 2,000 distinct microlensing events in the galactic bulge are detected and monitored by the OGLE and MOA teams. A small percentage of these are found to occur within $5''$ of each other and more than 10 days apart. If such a match consists of distinct events, we label them as recurring microlensing events. We present a systematic search for recurring events using data from OGLE and MOA. We restricted our search to matches with one of the events in 2013 and we determined that the dataset comprised of the 32 matches that fulfill these criteria contains 8 pairs of genuine repeating events, 5 pairs with the same double-peaked event, 17 pairs of false recurring events, 1 inconclusive and 1 non-microlensing match. From the 18 pairs that had the same event observed once by OGLE and once by MOA, we also found that the OGLE and MOA fields are offset with a mean $\mu = 3.51''$ and standard deviation $\sigma = 1.44''$. Furthermore, we identify the most interesting matches for further study and we discuss how these results could propel the discovery of planetary systems and high velocity objects through microlensing.

1. Introduction

1.1. Gravitational lensing

One of the most important predictions of Einstein’s Theory of Relativity is the deviation of photon trajectories from a straight line in the presence of strong gravitational fields. Subsequent astronomical observations have confirmed this result through the study of gravitational lensing, a process in which light from distant objects is bent when it passes another massive object and converges to form a secondary image of the background source. Analogous to the case of light distortion by a glass lens, the system can be described by an angular scale, the Einstein radius θ_E which represents the angular radius of the image in a perfectly aligned configuration, and a magnification coefficient, μ , the ratio of image to source area. These parameters can be further manipulated to determine physical properties of the system at hand. As a result, gravitational lensing is employed to study objects that are too faint to be observed through any another method, objects of unknown nature such as dark matter or even mass distribution on scales as large as the universe (Narayan & Bartelmann 2008).

Gravitational lensing phenomena can be classified based on the scale of the system. In particular, masses of the lens and source and distances to and within the configuration are parameters which determine the strength of gravitational lensing. The stronger effects occur in lensing by objects of masse on the order of $10^{11}M_{\odot}$ and larger (galaxies and galaxy clusters) at distance scales of Mpcs and Gpcs (Fig 1 - left), whereas microlensing events are produced by masses comparable to M_{\odot} only kpcs away. The corresponding Einstein radius for these configurations is on the order of 1 arcsecond in the former case and only 1 miliarcsecond in the later. This renders source images in the microlensing events unobservable with current instruments. However, a separation between the lens and the source less than θ_E corresponds to a magnification $\mu = 1.34$ in size. This is also equivalent to a 1.34 flux ratio (0.32 mag) since the surface brightness of the image and that of the source are the same (Narayan & Bartelmann 2008). Thus, in the study of gravitational microlensing, we are interested in the relative brightness of the source rather than its image (Fig 1 - right).

Fig. 1.— Left: lensing on cosmological scale. Right: typical microlensing light curve.

1.2. Microlensing events

In gravitational microlensing, the source and the lens have relative proper motions such that the Einstein radius of the system can be traversed within months, even days. As a consequence, microlensing events are finite in duration, in contrast to cosmological lensing when the effects can be observed on scales of Myr even for galaxies with high proper motions. For this reason, microlensing phenomena are referred to as events. Since microlensing is usually employed to measure properties of near-by faint objects, we lack the information about distances or velocity that we could normally measure for galaxies. However, we can measure a time scale for these events, given by the time it takes for the source to cross the Einstein ring. This is referred to as the Einstein diameter crossing time, τ_E and it also represents the time for which the magnification obeys $\mu \geq 1.34$ (Di Stefano 2012b). The observable τ_E is related to other physical parameters as follows (Di Stefano 2012a):

$$\tau_E = 3.86 \text{ days} \left(\frac{25 \text{ km s}^{-1}}{v} \right) \left(\frac{D_L}{100 \text{ pc}} \right)^{1/2} \left(\frac{M}{M_{\text{Jupiter}}} \right)^{1/2} \left(1 - \frac{D_L}{D_S} \right)^{1/2} \quad (1)$$

where v is the relative transverse velocity of the lens and the source, D_L and D_S the distance to the source and lens respectively, and M the mass of the lens. The Einstein crossing times can therefore be of order a few days to a few hundreds of days. To summarize, a microlensing event features a light curve for which we can measure two observables: the

Einstein crossing time, τ_E , and the magnification, μ . According to equation (1), there is a degeneracy in the number of system parameters and observables. However, several additional techniques such as the parallax effect due to the acceleration of the Earth, observations from space and recurring microlensing events (Narayan & Bartelmann 2008) can provide additional observables. Furthermore, there are certain distinctive features in the light curve of a microlensing event: there is a transient increase in the flux, the light curve is achromatic (magnification independent of wavelength) and symmetric relative to the peak. While these criteria can in principle be used to distinguish microlensing events from variable stars and novae, microlensing configurations are diverse in nature and can exhibit some of these features in their light curves. Consequently, the determination of whether an event that looks like microlensing is actually microlensing has to be made on a case by case basis.

1.3. Microlensing surveys

The most active survey teams in the field are the Optical Gravitational Lensing Experiment OGLE, a Poland/USA collaboration (Udalski 2003) and Microlensing Observation in Astrophysics MOA, a Japan/NZ collaboration (Bond et al. 2001). Both OGLE and MOA use ground-based telescopes to observe highly dense fields in the galactic bulge. Currently in its fourth phase, the OGLE team monitors about 340 million stars in a total of 267 fields with covering 92 deg² of the galactic bulge (Szymanski et al. 2011). The distribution of field cadences is as follows: 3 fields with a sample rate of 10-30 per night, 6 fields with 3-10 per night, 12 with 1-3 per night and more than 200 fields with less than one sample per night. During its second phase, the MOA team surveys 42 deg² of sky in 22 bulge fields with an average sample rate 6 per night (Sumi et al. 2013). Both teams have an automated warning system that sends out notifications when a new microlensing event is observed. Within the past observing season (2012), OGLE and MOA have found about 1700¹ and 700² events respectively, with only 430 events detected by both. Together, OGLE and MOA produce around 2,000 microlensing observations per year.

¹<http://ogle.astrouw.edu.pl/>

²<http://www.phys.canterbury.ac.nz/moa/>

1.4. Recurring microlensing events

Although there is not much literature on recurring events, an attempt to define the concept was made by (Skowron et al. 2009) who describe repeating microlensing events as being characterized by "a second brightening episode well after the first one such that the star has (largely) returned to its baseline". We refine this definition by stating that only events within $5''$ of each other and separated by more than 10 days should be considered. The reason for this addition is conferring a spatial and temporal location to the secondary peak and avoid repetitions in the dataset as much as possible.

The choice of observation field for OGLE and MOA is justified by the low rate of microlensing events and optical depth. The optical depth is defined to be the probability of a given star being within θ_E from another star (Narayan & Bartelmann 2008). The most recent estimates of the highest event rate and optical depth using MOA data are $1.45 \pm 0.67 \times 10^{-4} \text{star}^{-1} \text{yr}^{-1}$ and $1.05 \pm 0.08 \times 10^{-5}$ in the galactic bulge (Sumi et al. 2013). Thus, microlensing events are quite rare even in dense fields and therefore should not repeat. However, binarity in the source or lens, or a fast moving lens increase the probability such that we can expect about 1% of all microlensing events to be repeating (Di Stefano & Mao 1996).

As we can see from the expression for τ_E , the technique of microlensing observations could be highly efficient in the detection of small mass objects such as planets at large distances. In fact, it has been hypothesized that Earth-mass planets in the habitable zone of stars kpcs away could be discovered through microlensing (Gould 2005). Furthermore, with repeating microlensing events, the mass ratio of the components is given by the square of the ratio of the Einstein crossing time of the two events and one can easily determine whether the binary system is in fact a planetary system. Therefore, the method of repeating microlensing events would have no bias towards binary systems of higher mass or higher separation which can prove to be very effective in probing a larger selection of planetary systems (Mao et al. 2008).

1.5. Motivation and objectives

Microensing is one of the five techniques for planet detection. However, to date, only 25 of the 1047 confirmed planets ³ have been found through microlensing and none of these through repeating microlensing events. Our interest for recurring microlensing events stems from the fact that a large fraction of the recurring events could be due to planetary systems. If this were the case, the number of planets detected through microlensing could increase significantly in the years to come. The first step in developing this technique for finding planets is finding the actual recurring events, which is a non-trivial task. Thus, Section 2 of this paper is devoted to presenting the data and the procedures we employed to achieve the desired results. In Section 3 we present the results and in Sections 4 and 5 we discuss our findings and offer recommendations for future research.

2. Methods

2.1. Data

In this research, we use the observational data of microlensing events collected by the OGLE Early Warning System (EWS) and the MOA Transient Alert System in real time. The two datasets are structured differently: the OGLE photometric data is automatically reduced, aggregated by day and given in magnitudes over time, whereas the MOA photometric data is not aggregated by day and it is given in flux relative to the baseline over time. In addition to the observational data, we also use the results of the automated data analysis systems implemented on OGLE and MOA. These systems fit a point lens model to the data and return the parameters θ_E , μ and a plot of the fit overlaid onto the data. The initial dataset contains a total of 1857 microlensing events matches, each component of the match separated by less than 5" from the other and detected between 2005 and 2013. Furthermore, we use the results of ADS (Kurtz et al. 1999) and VizieR (Ochsenbein, Bauer, & Marcout 2000) searches within 5" of each of the matches.

³<http://exoplanet.eu/>

2.2. Procedures

We start with a table with basic information about the 1857 matches ⁴. This data contains the names of events, positions, lens parameters τ_E , μ as computed by OGLE/MOA, time of peak and spatial and temporal separation of a match. The first step in the data analysis is the selection of relevant data. For the scope of this study, we restrict our dataset to matches with the two events separated by more than 10 days and at least one event having occurred in 2013. Thus, we perform a query on these criteria.

Fig. 2.— A schematic representation of the data analysis processes. Continuous arrows represent semi-automated processes and the dotted arrows represent manual processes.

⁴Compiled and updated daily by Frank Primini

This reduced datasets contains all matches to be analyzed. For each of these matches, we complete the 4th, 5th and 6th level of the above diagram. We first extract the coordinates from the table and then do automated searches in the ADS database and VizieR catalogs using a Python⁵ script. We retrieve the ADS abstracts of papers which reference objects within 5" of a match and the closest 5 VizieR object and add them to our data. Similarly, we extract the name of the event from the table and use it to retrieve the files with photometric information for the event from the MOA and/or OGLE websites. While the OGLE data is already calibrated to magnitudes, the MOA is data is given in flux and needs additional calibration information . We obtain this manually since it is posted as an image file on the MOA website. In addition, we retrieve the plots of the photometric data fitted with a point mass lens model. Since the photometric data files are quite large ($> 20,000$ data points), these plots are used for the initial data exploration and to extract plotting parameters such as the duration of the event and magnitude or flux limits. Despite the differences in the OGLE and MOA data, a simple visual inspection of these plots can provide valuable information about the nature of the match.

After the initial inspection of the plots, we load the data into Python, reduce it, put it into a dataframe and then select the relevant data using the plotting parameters obtained before. In this context, relevant data refers to the photometric measurements for the event itself, ignoring the baseline outside of the event. At this step, we also handle any unusual features in the data such as missing values or partial information which arise from the photometric data not being loaded properly onto the website or a failure of the sensors during an observing session. Using the MOA calibration information, we then convert flux into magnitudes for any MOA event. With a quick visual inspection, we can also establish whether the calibration information is sensible. If this is not the case, we return the webpage of the event and retrieve the last 5 measurements of the baseline magnitude found by MOA. These measurements will not normally be in the photometry dataset since they might be taken well after the event has completed. We take an average of these values and set it to be the magnitude of the baseline (0 flux) and perform further calibration. After completing

⁵Python Software Foundation. Python Language Ref., version 2.7. Available at <http://www.python.org>

the calibration process for MOA, we compute a magnitude average in a window centered on the peak for both events. The size of the window is chosen such that it includes about 75% of the datapoints and thus depends on the event. We use the difference in the averages to normalize one of the light curves. Note that this step is necessary even if the both events in a match were detected by OGLE since distinct observation fields might be calibrated differently. Only now we can overplot the two light curves and successfully analyze them visually to determine the nature of the events and whether the two events in the match could be the same event.

Using these three pieces of information, the ADS abstracts, the Vizier objects and the overplotted light curves for two matching events, we determine whether a match is a genuine recurring event, a false recurring event or a false microlensing event.

3. Results

3.1. Principal results

In initial dataset which contains all the 1857 matches, 421 matches were found to have at least one event occurring in 2013. Further selections yielded that only 32 of these matches have a time offset larger than 10 days. Through the analysis of the 32 matches, we found 8 genuine recurring events, 5 double-peaked events, 17 false recurring events, 1 inconclusive match and 1 non-microlensing event. The double-peaked events are events with two merged light curves, but still two peaks which appear as one recurring event because the peaks were fitted independently. Although the peaks might be more than 10 days apart, these events don't match the description of a recurring event since the light curve does not return to the baseline in between the peaks. However, these matches are most likely the result of close binaries, possibly planetary systems which fits well within the scope of this study. Thus, instead of classifying these as false recurring events, we place them in a separate category subject to further study.

The diagram in Fig. 3 shows that the time difference between the recurring events in a real match is on average larger than the time difference in a false match. We found that the average time offset in real pairs is 1302 days, whereas the average time offset in false

Fig. 3.— Distribution of event matches. Bars represent the time difference between events.

pairs is 46 days. However, the average spatial separation between events in a real match is $3.7''$, comparable to the average separation of $3.5''$ between events in a false match. This unexpected result will be investigated further in Section 3.2.

3.1.1. *Genuine recurring events*

We summarize the parameters of the 8 genuine recurring events in Table 1. If we assume these event matches are due to binary systems or a fast moving lens, we can obtain an estimate of the mass ratio of the components from equation (1) by setting the velocities of the objects equal to each other. This is of course just a first-order approximation since a planet will have some additional positive or negative velocity due to its revolution around the star. We plot the Einstein crossing times and the mass ratio of the objects derived from the Einstein times in Fig. 4.

Table 1: Genuine repeating events.

No.	Event 1	τ_E (d)	μ	Event 2	τ_E (d)	μ	Sep (")	Δt (d)
1	ogle-2006-BLG-206	4.57	0.57	ogle-2013-BLG-1634	2.731	0.33	0.57	2666
2	ogle-2006-BLG-472	2.747	0.86	ogle-2013-BLG-1023	72.06	0.42	4.34	2496
3	moa-2007-BLG-126	171.5	...	ogle-2013-BLG-0042	37.5	0.55	4.33	2144
4	ogle-2008-BLG-286	36.5	0.034	moa-2013-BLG-551	107.9	0.0039	4.79	1915
5	ogle-2011-BLG-0989	17.6	1.11	moa-2013-BLG-239	2.09	6.89	3.82	647
6	ogle-2012-BLG-0443	17.7	0.077	ogle-2013-BLG-1114	55.18	0.01	4.02	429
7	ogle-2013-BLG-1066	8.37	0.064	moa-2013-BLG-478	840	0.86	3.44	63.8
8	ogle-2013-BLG-0467	44.8	0.025	ogle-2013-BLG-0847	40.2	0.22	4.05	62.8

Fig. 4.— Left: Einstein crossing times. Right: mass ratios of objects in real repeats

The mass ratio plot in Fig. 4 indicates that matches 3, 5 and 8 are good planetary system candidates. In addition, the ratios close to unity in matches 2 and 7 suggest that we could have a fast-moving object lensing two background sources at different times.

3.1.2. Double-peaked events

We present the data for the double-peaked events in Table 2. Fig 4. shows two such matches, each containing two copies of the same double-peaked event discovered through

the normalization and overlay of the light curves. In the first plot, MOA detected the first peak and OGLE the second one, while in the second plot, MOA found the second peak and OGLE the first one. We present the plots provided by MOA and OGLE for Event #5 for comparison in the Appendix.

Table 2: Double-peaked events.

No.	Event #1	τ_E (d)	μ	Event#2	τ_E (d)	μ	Sep (")	Δt (d)
1	ogle-2013-BLG-0017	23.6	1.21	moa-2013-BLG-021	4604	0.0042	0.46	175
2	ogle-2012-BLG-1536	64.0	1.10	moa-2013-BLG-190	110339	...	4.84	169
3	ogle-2013-BLG-1835	0.53	0.55	moa-2013-BLG-605	20.6	0.091	4.54	38
4	ogle-2013-BLG-0102	2.11	0.39	moa-2013-BLG-127	3.32	7.48	4.00	32
5	moa-2013-BLG-408	3.31	38.7	ogle-2013-BLG-0108	424	0.075	3.31	32

Fig. 5.— Overplotted light curves for match #5 (left) and match #4 (right)

3.1.3. Non-recurring events

We identified three types of matches that we classified as non-recurring events: false recurring events, noisy, inconclusive matches, and non-lensing events. We found 17 false

recurring events, 1 inconclusive match and 1 non-lensing event. The false recurring events can be further classified as follows:

1. MOA-OGLE offset: MOA and OGLE detect the same event, but due to errors in right ascension, declination and variations in fit parameters such as the time of the peak, they are detected as recurring events. These constitute 11 of the 17 false repeating events. Fig. 6 shows an overplot of the light curves for such a match. We also present the plots provided by OGLE and MOA in the Appendix for comparison.

Fig. 6.— Overplotted light curves for the same event detected by both MOA and OGLE

2. Ongoing events: a downside of choosing matches with one event in 2013 is that some of these events have not yet completed. If one such event is detected by both OGLE and MOA, they will both fit the incomplete light curve and report parameters independently. Since the data is highly degenerate, the predicted times of the peaks and Einstein crossing times will most likely be very different. Therefore, we can expect these events to have a reported separation in time greater than 10 days and in fact, these matches constitute 5 of the false recurring events. Fig. 7 shows an overplot of the light curves for such a match.

Fig. 7.— Overplotted light curves for the same event detected by both MOA and OGLE

3. Distinct OGLE observing fields: OGLE observes in over 200 fields in one night. Some of these fields overlap at the edges and it is thus possible to find events which were detected twice by OGLE. Once again, due to inconsistencies in position measurements and fit parameters, these matches pass as recurring events. Fig 8. shows the ogle fields labeled by numbers and colored based on how many times a night OGLE samples these. Only 1 of these matches was found in the dataset: one event detected in both 500 and 505 fields.

The data also includes 1 inconclusive match and 1 non-microlensing event. The inconclusive match was labeled as such due to the noisiness of the MOA data which makes overplotting not very effective in determining whether it is the same event or not. In addition, there is a non-lensing event characterized as such due to the high magnification, asymmetry in the light curve and a secondary highly asymmetric peak. To date, the ADS and Visier searches have not returned any relevant results for this object. Fig 9. shows the light curves of both the inconclusive and the non-lensing events.

Fig. 8.— Image of OGLE fields taken from <http://ogle.astrouw.edu.pl/>. Color codes: red ~ 10 -30 samples/night, yellow ~ 3 -10 samples/night, green ~ 1 -3 samples/night, others < 1 samples/night

Fig. 9.— Left: inconclusive result. Right: non-lensing event.

3.2. Secondary results

The results presented in the previous section show that about 18 false recurring and double peaked matches have significant position offsets in the MOA-OGLE data and thus they are detected as recurring rather than the same event. It is important to note that in the initial dataset of recurring events, the MOA-OGLE matches found by the two teams are eliminated. Thus, these additional 18 matches have not been classified as being the same event by either MOA or OGLE. We therefore compare the separations of the MOA-OGLE matches in our sample with the 435 MOA-OGLE matches identified by MOA in the 2013 observing season. Fig. 9. shows the separations in the two samples overplotted on the same histogram.

Fig. 10.— Histogram of MOA-OGLE event matches in 2013

Basic statistics performed on the two samples shows that the sample found by MOA has a mean $\mu = 0.55''$ and standard deviation $\sigma = 0.38''$, whereas our sample has $\mu = 3.51''$ and $\sigma = 1.44''$.

4. Analysis

4.1. Discussion

Of the 32 events that passed the first two selection criteria, about 25% of these were confirmed to be real recurring events. Assuming that all of them are the result of a binary lens or source, the plot of mass ratios indicate that a few binaries could actually be planetary systems. If we expanded this dataset to include all 1857 matches, we could expect about 400 real recurring events of which around 100 could be due to planetary systems. This would overturn the current state of the field of microlensing in which only about 25 planets in 23 planetary systems have been confirmed. Therefore, in theory, the observational technique of recurring events could prove to be a very reliable method of planetary detection. In addition, 5 of the 32 events were found to be double-peaked which is also evidence of binarity. MOA and OGLE use point mass fits and as a consequence each will only detect one peak. However, assuming no prior biases, there is a 50% chance that MOA will detect one peak and OGLE another one and the search for recurring events should be expected to turn up a few of these matches. The method of recurring events can therefore also be employed for finding close binaries or fast moving objects through double-peaked events. Furthermore, our sample of MOA-OGLE matches reveals a significant offset in the position MOA and OGLE provide for the same event. This offset is much larger than the one anticipated by the sample of MOA-OGLE matches found by MOA. The sample found by MOA does not include any of the 18 MOA-OGLE matches we confirmed by overplotting the light curves and 11 of these are outside of the distribution of separations of MOA-OGLE pairs.

4.2. Future directions

The next step is to further analyze the genuine repeating and double-peaked events and determine the nature of the source-lens systems. To do so, we need to abandon the point mass fits and create a model that accounts for multiple sources and multiple lenses. This is the current work of Prof. Di Stefano's team at the Harvard Center for Astrophysics. Furthermore, future research should account for the anomalous results in the position offset between MOA and OGLE. We found the majority of offsets to be in the range of 3"-5",

comparable to our definition radius of 5" for recurring events. As a result, it is possible that we have missed recurring events due to the large offsets. Thus, it is crucial to correct for this offset and recompile the lists of repeating events. As soon as these milestones are reached, we should then analyze all the ~ 1800 recurring events detected by OGLE and MOA between 2007 and 2013. The final goal of these additional studies is to turn microlensing into a competitive technique for planet detection.

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Fig. 11.— MOA-OGLE event match from MOA (<https://it019909.massey.ac.nz/moa/>) and OGLE (<http://ogle.astrouw.edu.pl/ogle4/ews/ews.html>)

Fig. 12.— Double peaked event from MOA (<https://it019909.massey.ac.nz/moa/>) and OGLE (<http://ogle.astrouw.edu.pl/ogle4/ews/ews.html>)